

Comparison of Surface Roughness and Microhardness of Two Different Nanohybrid Composites - An In Vitro Study

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION:

The restoration of the biological, functional, and cosmetic qualities of healthy tooth structure is the ultimate goal of employing a dental restorative material. The surface texture can be used to observe how the application of nanotechnology in composites containing nanoparticles has reduced the interstitial gaps between the inorganic particles, improving their physical qualities and polish maintenance. Rough surfaces encourage the retention of bacterial plaque, which later develops into periodontal disease. High quality finishing and polishing is one of the most important aspects of dental restorations since it increases their durability and aesthetic value.

AIM:

To assess and compare surface roughness and microhardness of two different nano hybrid composite materials.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

The two composites were made as discs. These composite disks are grouped into Group A - Neospectra ST(,Dentsply sirona,charlotte,NC,USA) nanohybrid composites and Group B - Gaenial (GC, Asia)

Surface roughness:

Stylus Profilometry of these disks were done and the raw data was obtained. Values were analyzed using Mann-whitney U Test in SPSS Software version 23.7.

Microhardness

Microhardness test was done using Vickers microhardness test. Values were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) test

RESULTS

From the study , Ra and Rz value was less for G Aenial whereas Rq value was high for G Aenial compared to Neospectrum composite with the p value of 0.3 and 0.74. No statistically significant difference in surface roughness was found in the nanohybrid composites tested in this study.G Aenial composites showed a statistically significant higher microhardness value when compared to neospectra with the p value of 0.045

CONCLUSION:

G Aenial composites had a smooth surface and better microhardness compared to neospectra composite.

KEYWORDS:

Gaenial,neospectra,Nanohybrid ,surface roughness ,microhardness, novel material

INTRODUCTION

Resin composites are the most preferred material in restorative dentistry due to its superior aesthetics, biocompatibility, adhesive qualities and strong mechanical properties. Since their introduction in dentistry, numerous strategies have been put forth to enhance the polymer matrix and filler technology [1,2]. Earlier resin composites had large filler particles and their polishability was not satisfactory.

Recent introduction of innovative nanocomposites have improved the clinical performance of restorations[3]. Nanofilled composites are a combination of both nanomers and nanoclusters [4,5], whereas Nanohybrid composites are of nano-fillers and hybrid fillers [6]. These composites are recommended as universal composites as they have the functional strength for posterior teeth and aesthetic characteristics for the anterior teeth[7,8].

Surface texture is considered as one of the essential factors for increased durability and excellent aesthetics of dental restorations[9]. Rough surfaces cause plaque buildup, gingival inflammation, periodontal issues, demineralization of enamel, discoloration, cavities, and poor aesthetics leading to failure of the restorations[10,11]. Surface qualities of composites could be affected by the composition and type of organic matrix, as well as the size, composition, and distribution of filler particles [12].

Microhardness of composite resins also plays a vital role in the clinical success and longevity of restorations. Higher microhardness of the restorative material can provide better wear resistance and abrasive resistance [13]. Hence, the current study was aimed to assess and compare surface roughness and microhardness of two different nano hybrid composite materials - G-aenial and Neo-spectra.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Two different nanohybrid resin composites , (n=15) were divided into 2 groups such as Group A Neo spectra ST(Dentsply sirona,charlotte,NC,USA) and Group B - Gaenial (GC, Asia) . Each composite discs of size 5mm x 2mm were fabricated in a cylindrical metallic mold at room temperature. The material was gently packed inside the mold. The mold was stabilized with two glass slabs on either sides to ensure a flat and uniform surface of the specimens. Mylar strips were placed in contact with either surfaces of the unpolymerized resin to avoid oxygen inhibition layer formation. The glass slab was pressed against the mold carefully to remove the excess material. Specimens were light irradiated with a light curing unit (Bluephase G4100-240V Curing light, Ivoclar 800mW/cm²) for 20 sec from both sides. Composite discs were removed from the mold and final finishing and polishing was performed(Sof -Lex, 3M, St Paul, Minnesota)

Surface roughness measurement:

Surface roughness was measured using a Surface Roughness Tester (Stylus profilometer SJ310 Mitutoyo). Three measurements were obtained in three different zones and averaged.

Microhardness measurement:

Microhardness of the test specimens were measured using Vickers microhardness tester (HMG, Shimadzu corporation, Kyoto, Japan). Images of 10X magnification were captured with the digital camera and the diagonal length of indentation was measured automatically

Statistical analysis:

Values were analyzed statistically using SPSS Software version 23.7. Shapiro- Wilks test was used to test the normality of data. Man-whitney U Test was used to compare the surface roughness(Ra, Rq, Rz) of each group. One-way ANOVA test was used to examine the statistical difference for microhardness in each group.

RESULTS:**SURFACE ROUGHNESS:**

Average Ra, Rq and Rz values of both groups are reported in Table 1. Mann whitney U test showed no statistical differences among both groups.

	Group A (NEOSPECTRA)	Group B (G-AENIAL)	P VALUE
MEAN VALUE (Ra)	5.80	5.20	0.347
MEAN VALUE (Rq)	4.90	6.10	0.530
MEAN VALUE (Rz)	5.80	5.20	0.754

Table 1 represents the Ra, Rq and Rz values of both neospectra and G-Aenial composites. Statistical analysis using Mann-Whitney U test showed that both groups had no statistically significant difference in surface roughness

Microhardness :

The mean value and standard deviation of each composite was calculated . One way ANOVA showed significant differences among the groups(TABLE 2)(Figure 1). Images were captured at 10X magnification for both groups (Figure 2)

GROUP	MEAN VALUE	STD.DEVIATION	P VALUE
NEOSPECTRA	40.7620	2.85993	0.045*
G-AENIAL	57.7140	6.97241	

Table 2 represents the mean and standard deviation of both neospectra and G-Aenial composites. Statistical analysis using one way ANOVA showed that both groups had statistically significant differences in microhardness.

Fig 1 Shows the microhardness comparison between Group A(Neospectra) and Group B (G-aenial)

Figure 2 shows the 10X magnification images of neospectra and G-aenial composites respectively which were seen under the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

DISCUSSION

Ideally a dental restorative material should mimic a healthy tooth structure in its biological, functional, and aesthetic characteristics. Currently no restorative material meets these ideal characteristics. Introduction of nanocomposites have improved the physical mechanical and aesthetic properties of composites. Nanocomposites having fillers with nanoparticle size reduces the interstitial spaces among the inorganic particles, providing better physical and mechanical properties which can be reflected in the surface characteristics too [14].

Surface roughness can lead to bacterial plaque retention, staining, gingival inflammation which may later progress into periodontal disease[15]. The surface roughness of composites are influenced by the microstructure and the polishing systems used to modify the surface characteristics. Among this, the type of organic matrix and characteristic of fillers exert a direct influence[16]. Nanohybrid resin composites improve the distribution of fillers in the matrix by combining nanoparticles with submicron particles to achieve a compact filler load[17]. G-aenial and NeoSpectra ST are the widely used nanohybrid composites all over the world, hence preferred for this study.

Surface roughness was measured using stylus profilometry. A mechanical probe was moved across the surface to establish its surface roughness. The probe traced the surface contours and its height at each location and analyzed the resulting 1D scan or 2D map. Surface Roughness was measured using variables like Ra, Rq and Rz, where Ra is the arithmetic average of the absolute values of all profile points, Rq is the root-mean-square values of all heights around the mean and RZ is the mean absolute value of the five most prominent peak's heights and the five darkest alleys' depths relative to the assessment length (R). However, they do not depict the difference in the size of the features and their shape.

The data of each composite has been analyzed. Mann-Whitney U Test was used for the statistical analysis of the two composites. There are significantly insignificant differences between the Ra values of neospectra and G-aenial, but there are no statistically significant differences between the Rq and Rz values of neospectra and G-aenial. Though the study showed that there is no significant difference between the two

composites, the values of Ra, Rz are relatively low for G-aenial composite, whereas its Rq is higher. The study infers that the G-aenial composites shows a slightly superior surface smoothness compared to neospectra, though the results are insignificant statistically as well as in clinical use.

Surface hardness influences the capability of the composites for finishing and polishing and also abrasion resistance[18]. This can directly influence the longevity of the restoration as it determines the chemical dissolution, abrasion resistance and ability to abrade the opposing dental structures[19,20,21]. Current study shows that the microhardness of G-aenial composites were higher than neospectra and it was statistically significant. These results can be attributed to the increased filler content of G-aenial composites. The image captured at 10X magnification also showed lesser irregularities for G-aenial composites

CONCLUSION:

Although there was no significant difference in surface roughness, G-aenial composites had better microhardness than neospectra. The present study was conducted in an invitro set up , hence may not simulate the exact oral environment. The specimens were not subjected to thermocycling also. Within the limitations of the study, it is concluded that the G-aenial composites have superior surface characteristics than neospectra and further clinical studies are required in this field.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: None

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